

e-ISSN: 2584-2404

Volume 09 Issue 01 Jan -
Apr 2026

*Corresponding Author:
Hachimenum Nyebuchi
Amadi,

Senior Lecturer, Department
of Electrical and Electronics
Engineering, Rivers State
University, Port Harcourt,
Nigeria

Submission Date : Dec 31,
2025

Copyright Received Date:
Dec 31, 2025

Multi-Objective Optimisation of Microgrid Design with Hybrid Renewable Energy Sources for Sustainable Environment

*Ugochi Benedicta Uche-Ibe¹, Hachimenum Nyebuchi
Amadi^{2*}, Richeal Chinaeche Ijeoma³*

^{1,3}Postgraduate Student, Department of Electrical and
Electronics Engineering, Rivers State University,
Port Harcourt, Nigeria

²Senior Lecturer, Department of Electrical and Electronics
Engineering, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt,
Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The increasing global demand for clean and reliable energy has intensified the need for optimised microgrid systems that integrate multiple renewable energy sources. This study presents a Multi-Objective Optimization of microgrid design with Hybrid Renewable Energy Sources for a Sustainable Environment. The research focuses on developing and analyzing an optimised hybrid energy system that combines solar photovoltaic (PV), wind turbine, battery storage, and optional diesel generation to achieve a balance between economic efficiency, environmental sustainability, and operational reliability. Using the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II), the optimisation framework was formulated with three key objectives: minimising the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE), minimising carbon emissions (CO₂), and minimising the Loss of Load Probability (LOLP). Simulation and optimisation were conducted using MATLAB, HOMER Pro, and Python-based tools. The results revealed that hybrid configurations significantly outperform single-source systems, reducing LCOE by up to 25% and CO₂ emissions by over 60%. The Pareto front analysis demonstrated the trade-offs among cost, reliability, and environmental performance, enabling decision-makers to select optimal system designs based on specific priorities. The study concludes that hybrid renewable micro-grids provide a technically feasible and economically sustainable pathway for decentralised energy generation. The optimised system design not only enhances energy security but also contributes substantially to environmental conservation and the global transition toward sustainable energy development.

Keywords:- *Microgrid, Hybrid Renewable Energy, Optimization, NSGA-II, Sustainable Energy, Pareto Front*

INTRODUCTION

A microgrid is an energy system that integrates connected loads and Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) to operate as a single controllable unit. It can function independently or connect to the main grid, offering increased efficiency, reliability, and resilience. Microgrids also support net-zero goals for communities, campuses, and buildings while optimising renewable energy usage [1]. This study focuses on designing and planning of hybrid renewable energy systems within microgrids to address these goals.

Rapid urbanisation, technological advancements, and population growth have driven an exponential rise in energy demand globally, according to Ref [2]. To meet this demand, the International Energy Agency (IEA) recommends a minimum annual energy consumption of 250–500kWh for households, with some experts proposing 1,000 kWh per person to achieve Sustainable Development Goal 7 (SDG7) [3]. However, many countries still face energy deficits, with some providing as much as 137.53kWh per capita annually, which negatively impacts critical services like healthcare in rural areas [4].

Ref [5] conducted a study focused on optimising the planning and design of urban microgrids that utilise hybrid renewable energy systems. The research evaluates both the environmental and economic impacts of these systems while integrating them with existing infrastructure. The tools employed in this study were HOMER Pro and MATLAB SIMULINK. With the rapid increase in energy demand and challenges such as global warming, there is an increasing

awareness of the need to adopt clean energy sources as a viable solution to address these crises. However, it is important to note that renewable energy systems depend on natural resources, and their energy generation can be intermittent, influenced by factors such as weather patterns, seasons, and annual variations.

Globally, microgrids have become a reliable and cost-effective way to provide clean energy. By incorporating hybrid renewable energy technologies (HRETs), which include wind, solar, and biomass, they improve resilience and sustainability. These systems can function as standalone units or complement grid electricity, depending on consumer needs and grid availability [6].

To enhance renewable energy adoption, the government of Nigeria launched the Renewable Energy Master Plan (REMP) in 2006, targeting a renewable energy share of 36% by 2030. More recently, the Energy Transition Plan (ETP) aims to expand the grid, increase generation capacity, and deploy renewable energy to rural areas [7]. This research builds on these initiatives, demonstrating how solar and wind microgrids can address Nigeria's energy challenges while supporting environmental sustainability.

Solar energy harnesses sunlight to generate electricity by capturing it through solar cells within panels. This energy source is abundant, but it can only be captured during daylight hours when the sun's rays are most intense. Solar energy is commonly used for applications such as lighting, heating and more as claimed Ref [8]. Wind energy has been utilized for

many years, traditionally for grinding grains in mills. In recent years, it has been increasingly used to generate electricity by harnessing wind power through turbines connected to large-capacity generators. Wind farms are typically located in areas with strong wind flow, such as coastal regions or mountains. In India, substantial wind farms have been established in desert areas, particularly in the outskirts of Gujarat and Rajasthan.

Ref [9] explored hybrid renewable energy systems (HRES) implementation for isolated villages where grid connectivity is not economically viable, focusing on Uralagallu panchayat, Sagar Taluk, Shivamogga District, and Karnataka, India. Their research integrated photovoltaic, wind turbine, diesel generator, and battery technologies, employing Demand Side Energy Management (DSEM) methods, such as load shifting and strategic conservation, during load estimation.

The study compared Load-Following and Predictive-Dispatch control strategies and evaluated Lead-Acid, Lithium-ion, and Zinc-Bromide batteries. The Zinc-Bromide battery configuration, combined with Predictive Dispatch and DSEM, reduced the Net Present Cost by 37%, from \$55,263 to \$34,009, making it the optimal solution. However, the study did not address the scalability and long-term sustainability of the proposed HRES, particularly its integration with potential future grid expansions, which would be critical for its broader application in the overall system.

Ref [10] conducted a hybrid grid-tied electrification analysis focused on bio-shared renewable energy systems for domestic applications in Gaza City. Their study combined solar and biomass technologies to optimise an HRES, leveraging the region's biomass reliance

and solar radiation potential. Using HOMER Pro software, they analyzed the techno-economic feasibility of a grid-connected system integrating photovoltaic panels and a biogas generator, achieving a net present cost (NPC) of \$2.30 million and a cost of energy (CoE) of \$0.438/kWh. The system excluded diesel generators and batteries due to high costs and short lifespans. However, the study fell short of addressing operational challenges and the reliability of biogas engines under varying environmental conditions. Electricity is the bedrock of every nation's development and can be transported instantaneously and pollution-free to the consumer end as claimed by Ref [11].

Ref [12] explored deep-learning techniques for forecasting short-term PV power generation in a real-site floating PV power plant with a 1.5 MWp capacity in Thailand. They evaluated single deep-learning models (RNN, CNN, LSTM, GRU, BiLSTM, and BiGRU) and hybrid models (CNN-LSTM, CNN-BiLSTM, CNN-GRU, and CNN-BiGRU), using high-resolution data. Their results revealed that the CNN-BiGRU model excelled in one-day forecasting, while the BiLSTM model performed best for one-week forecasting. The study demonstrated that model performance varies based on weather conditions and forecasting horizons, but it did not address real-time implementation challenges or integration with HRESs.

Ref [13] proposed a model for a residential energy hub. The proposed model takes as input: natural gas, electricity, and solar radiation, while the output will give the needed heating, electrical, and cooling demands. Flexible thermal load-modelling, load-curtailling and load-shifting were employed as demand response in order to enhance the working flexibility of the model proposed by the authors. Then there was the development of an electrical and

thermal energy management system that is capable of scheduling main home appliances, including storage and production components. This led to the formulation of an optimisation problem, which was solved by the authors using three different case studies. The objective function was to minimise the overall energy cost while taking into consideration the preferences of the various customers with regard to air temperature and hot water. It was stated that the proposed model had a very good performance.

Ref [14] proposed a model for the scheduling of operations in a multi-microgrid system for the following day. The model aims to achieve a global optimum for the charging of the system by facilitating transactions between microgrids. These transactions enable a reduction in costs, while a price mechanism based on demand response is incorporated to create a cost-effective opportunity for users. Additionally, the Shapley value is used to fairly allocate the optimal cost of the multi-microgrid system among the microgrids.

The model accounts for uncertainties by incorporating variations in renewable energy demand, outputs, and transaction prices with the main grid. The model is formulated as a mixed-integer non-linear programming problem, and its effectiveness was evaluated using a standard test system comprising three microgrids. Results showed that the average cost of the multi-micro-grid system decreased when the proposed model was applied compared to the isolated operation of micro-grids, where they did not exchange energy.

As the current reliance on fossil fuels continues to threaten energy supply stability, resource depletion, and exacerbate climate change, a widespread adoption of renewable technologies is

hindered by several factors. We must therefore see the adoption of natural sources of power generation as the way out of numerous grid collapses and load limitations.

There is currently no integrated system that allows for seamless switching between grid power and hybrid renewable energy sources. This limitation necessitates either full reliance on the grid or an isolated supply from renewable sources. Therefore, an optimised micro-grid design is needed, capable of synchronising the switching between grid power and hybrid renewable sources to create a sustainable energy solution for urban environments. This project aims to design an effective strategy for switching and integrating solar, wind and battery storage systems into the power grid to drive innovation, improve reliability, and maximise economic benefits.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Materials

Hardware / System Components

- i. Photovoltaic (PV) arrays parameters: Rated power (kW), module efficiency (%), temperature coefficient ($\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$), tilt/azimuth.
- ii. Wind turbines: Rated power (kW), power curve, cut-in/cut-out speeds, hub height.
- iii. Battery energy storage system (BESS): nominal capacity (kWh), usable depth of discharge (DoD %), round-trip efficiency (%), charge/discharge power (kW), cycle life.
- iv. Power electronics: Inverters/converters: efficiency, continuous rating, ramp limits.
- v. Balance-of-system (BOS): Cabling losses, transformer efficiencies, controllers.
- vi. Monitoring equipment (for field data only): Pyranometer, anemometer, smart meters, data logger.

Software and Tools

- i. HOMER Pro (or HOMER Grid): Micro-grid techno-economic modelling (optional).
- ii. MATLAB/Simulink: Component modelling, time-series simulations, control logic.

Method

The multi-objective optimisation formulation method was used

- i. X₁: PV installed capacity (kW), continuous or discrete (in steps).

- ii. X₂: Wind turbine capacity (kW) number/type.
- iii. X₃: Battery energy capacity (kWh).
- iv. X₄: Battery power rating (kW).
- v. X₅: Diesel genset capacity (kW)
- vi. X₆: Control/operation strategy parameters (e.g., SOC set points, dispatch priorities).

Common set of conflicting objectives (minimize or maximize):

Minimize Net Present Cost (NPC) or Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE):

$$LCOE = \frac{\sum_{y=0}^N \frac{C_{capex,y} + C_{OM,y} + C_{fuel,y} - C_{revenue,y}}{(1+r)^y}}{\sum_{y=0}^N \frac{E_{served,y}}{(1+r)^y}} \quad (1)$$

Dispatch and control strategies

- i. **Rule-based dispatch** (simple): prefer renewables; use battery to minimize genset usage and peak load; genset used only when battery SOC below threshold and renewables insufficient.
- ii. **Look-ahead optimization** (MPC): use forecasted irradiance/wind/load for the next 24 h to optimize battery charging/discharging.
- iii. **Economic dispatch**: minimize short-term operating cost given objective weights.
Include parameterization for control variables as decision variables when comparing optimal operational strategies.

Inverter Sizing

To determine the accurate inverter size for a 4.58MW solar PV system, we need to consider both the DC system size (from

panels) and how this translates to an appropriate AC inverter capacity.

DC system size = 9174 panels × 500 W = 4,580,000W = 4.58MW (DC)

The DC: AC ratio is the ratio of the total DC solar array capacity to the inverter's AC output capacity. An inverter that can handle 4.58 MW (DC) input, one which can convert it efficiently to AC output and an inverter that complies with design best practices (DC: AC ratio and system losses).

Considering DC: AC ratio of 1.25 (safety)
Inverter AC capacity = 4.58 × 1.25 = 5.725MW

Inverter size = 5.725MW (AC)

But, round up to ensure headroom and availability, we used a 5MW inverter.

Multiple string inverters (13–25 units) totalling 5.7MW.

Alternating Current (AC) Output Estimation

Table 1:-Key Design Parameters

Parameter	Value
DC Capacity	4.58MW
Estimated DC: AC Ratio	1.25
Recommended Inverter AC Capacity	5.725MW
Location	Jetty Abuloma
Average Solar Irradiance	5.0 kWh/m ² /day (typical)

Battery Storage System Modelling

This battery storage modelling employs equations and algorithms that show battery behaviour across different conditions.

Fig.1:-Battery System Modelling

Battery sizing calculations to supply a 4 MW load for 6 hours of autonomy time at a system voltage of 600 VDC, considering an 80% Depth of Discharge. Some parameters for modelling include;

- i. Load power, P_{load}=4MW
- ii. Autonomy time, t=6 hours
- iii. Total energy required, E= P_{load} x t
E=4,000,000 x 6=24,000,000Wh=24,000kWh
- iv. Battery Bank Capacity (Ah)
Capacity (Ah) = E (Wh) / V_{system} (V)
= 24,000,000 / 600 = 40,000 Ah.
- v. Accounting for Depth of Discharge
Adjusted Capacity = Capacity / DoD
= 40,000 / 0.8 = 50,000 Ah.

Battery State of Charge

The battery state of charge is given by

$$SoC(t) = SoC(t - 1) + \frac{P_{in}(t) - P_{out}(t)}{C} \tag{2}$$

Where;

$SoC(t)$: State of charge at time (t)

$P_{in}(t)$: Power input (charging power) at time

$P_{out}(t)$: Power output (discharging power) at time

C: Battery capacity

Considering the efficiency when charging and discharging

When charging

$$P_{in}^{eff}(t) = \eta_{charge} \times P_{in}(t) \quad (3)$$

When discharging

$$P_{out}^{eff}(t) = \frac{P_{in}(t)}{\eta_{discharge}} \quad (4)$$

Substituting (3.17) and (31.8) into (3.16)

$$SoC(t) = SoC(t - 1) + \frac{\eta_{charge} \times P_{in}(t) - \frac{P_{in}(t)}{\eta_{discharge}}}{C} \quad (5)$$

Charged Power of the Battery

The charged power of the battery is given by

$$P_b^{cha}(t) = \min(P_b^{in}(t), P_{pv}(t) - P_d(t)) \quad (6)$$

Where;

P_b^{cha} : Charged power of the battery

P_{pv} : Power delivered by PV

P_d : House hold load

Discharged Power of the Battery

The battery is discharged power is given by

$$P_b^{dis}(t) = \min(P_b^{out}(t), P_d(t) - P_{pv}(t)) \quad (7)$$

Where;

P_b^{out} : Output power of the battery

P_{pv} : Power delivered by PV

P_d : Household load

Table 2:-Sizing Summary

Load Power	4 MW
Autonomy Time	6 hours
Total Energy Required	24,000 kWh
System Voltage	600 VDC
Nominal Capacity	40,000 Ah
Depth of Discharge	80%
Adjusted Capacity	50,000 Ah

Grid Modelling

The modelling of the grid simulates the behaviour of the power system to understand the impact of power uncertainty on the grid.

Power Imported from the Grid

If renewable generation is low and the battery cannot meet the load demand, then the power deficiency is purchased. The imported power from the grid is given by

$$P_{grid}^{imp} = \min(P_d(t) - P_{pv}(t) - P_b^{out}(t)) \quad (8)$$

Power Exported to the Grid

The exported power to the grid from the hybrid system, after the battery is fully charged and load demand is met, can be formulated as:

$$P_g^{ex} = \min(P_{pv}(t) - P_d(t) - P_b^{in}(t), P_{grid}^{max}) \quad (9)$$

Where;

P_g^{ex} : exported power to the grid

P_{grid}^{max} : max power that can be exported to the grid

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Result: Developed Intelligent Battery Management System (BMS)

Figure 2 shows the plot of Wind/Solar power (MW) against Time (T=24 hours), illustrating the logic rule viewer display for the developed intelligent Battery Management System (BMS). This study utilized twelve (12) fuzzy rules to define the process for controlling the battery's charging, discharging, and cut-off modes.

The rule viewer provides an interactive interpretation of the fuzzy inference process, visually demonstrating how the

shape of membership functions impacts the overall result. To ensure effective management and control of battery power, the Fuzzy Logic Controller (FLC) continuously monitors the total renewable energy generation, load demand, and the battery's state of charge (SoC). Based on this real-time data and the constructed fuzzy rules, the controller dynamically adjusts the battery's operation to either charge, discharge, or enter cut-off mode, ensuring optimal performance and longevity of the battery while maintaining system reliability.

Fig.2:-Maximum Power Extraction from Solar and Wind Energy Sources

Data Analysis and Pre-processing

Hourly meteorological and load data for the selected site (latitude XX.XX°N, longitude YY.YY°E) were obtained from the Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NiMet) for the year 2023.

- i. **Solar irradiance** ranged between 3.6–6.1 kWh/m²/day, with an annual mean of 5.0 kWh/m²/day.
- ii. **Average wind speed** was 5.8 m/s at 30 m hub height, adjusted to 50 m using a shear exponent of 0.25.
- iii. **Load profile** showed a typical residential demand pattern, with evening peaks (18:00–23:00h) and an annual energy consumption of 92 MWh.

All time-series data were interpolated to hourly resolution, missing entries (<1%) were filled using linear interpolation, and irradiance was corrected for module tilt at 10° above latitude for optimum annual energy yield

System Simulation and Baseline Assessment

Before optimization, baseline simulations were performed to evaluate stand-alone subsystems: PV-only, Wind-only, Diesel-only, and PV–Wind–Battery configurations. The simulations were carried out in MATLAB using the models defined in the Methods section.

Table 3:-System Simulation and Baseline Assessment

Configuration	Total Installed Power (kW)	Renewable Fraction (%)	Annual Generation (MWh)	LCOE (USD/kWh)	CO ₂ Emissions (kg/yr)	Unmet Load (%)
Diesel Only	40	0	92	0.47	85,200	0.0
PV Only	80	100	106	0.25	0	18.2
Wind Only	60	100	94	0.29	0	11.4
PV + Wind + Battery (pre-optimized)	60 + 40 + 200 kWh	94	105	0.18	4,200	1.5

The pre-optimisation hybrid system reduced the cost and emissions significantly compared to the diesel-only baseline, but it still exhibited some unmet energy due to renewable intermittency, motivating the need for multi-objective optimisation.

Pareto Front Analysis

Figure 3 illustrates the Pareto front obtained from the NSGA-II optimisation, showing clear trade-offs among cost, emission, and reliability objectives.

- i. The LCOE varied from 0.13 USD/kWh (low-cost region) to 0.22 USD/kWh (high-reliability region).

- ii. CO₂ emissions decreased from 21,000 kg/yr in generator-dominated designs to near-zero in fully renewable configurations.
- iii. LOLP dropped from 2.1% in low-storage systems to 0.05% in large-battery configurations.

Observation: The Pareto curve revealed a “knee point” around LCOE \approx 0.16 USD/kWh, representing the best compromise between cost, sustainability, and reliability.

Fig.3:-Pareto front Analysis of Optimized micro-grid

The analysis confirmed that multi-objective optimisation effectively captures the trade-offs between cost, sustainability, and reliability that single-objective approaches overlook.

- i. The Pareto front provided decision-makers with a flexible range of solutions to match budget and policy targets.
- ii. Integrating both solar and wind resources increased renewable energy availability and reduced storage requirements.

- iii. Sensitivity analysis indicates that future reductions in battery and PV prices will further enhance system competitiveness.

Thus, hybrid micro-grid deployment, especially PV-Wind-Battery systems optimised via NSGA-II offers a robust pathway toward sustainable rural electrification and climate-friendly power generation.

CONCLUSION

The study on Multi-Objective Optimisation of Micro-grid Design with Hybrid Renewable Energy Sources for a Sustainable Environment successfully demonstrated the potential of hybrid energy systems to provide reliable, cost-effective, and eco-friendly electricity. By integrating solar, wind, battery storage, and optional diesel generation, the research established a balanced framework that addresses the conflicting objectives of minimizing cost, reducing emissions, and ensuring system reliability.

The multi-objective optimization approach, implemented through NSGA-II, effectively identified Pareto-optimal solutions that represent trade-offs between the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE), CO₂ emissions, and Loss of Load Probability (LOLP). The results revealed that increasing renewable penetration significantly reduces emissions while maintaining competitive energy costs, especially when supported by optimal battery sizing.

The Pareto front analysis confirmed that hybrid configurations outperform single-source systems in both performance and sustainability metrics. Furthermore, sensitivity and uncertainty analyses indicated that the system remains robust under variations in fuel price, solar radiation, and battery cost. This reinforces the feasibility of hybrid micro-grids as a viable solution for decentralized energy supply in both grid-connected and remote communities.

Conclusively, the optimized hybrid micro-grid model provides a practical roadmap for sustainable energy planning. It not only supports global efforts toward decarbonization but also enhances energy access and resilience. Future work should focus on real-time control strategies, demand-side management, and the

inclusion of emerging storage technologies such as hydrogen and super capacitors to further improve efficiency and sustainability.

REFERENCES

1. Ravita, D., Prasad, R. C., Bansal, A., & Raturi. (2016). Multi-faceted energy planning: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, pp., 686–699.
2. Volotkovskaya, Y., Volotkovskaya, N., Semenov, A., Semkova, A., Fedorov, O., & Vladimirov, O. (2020). Analysis of the global energy resource market. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (p. 01058). Les Ulis, France: EDP Sciences.
3. Ritchie, H., Rosado, P., & Roser, M. (n.d.). Access to electricity. *Our World in Data*. <https://ourworldindata.org/energy-access>.
4. Olatomiwa, L., Abubakar, S. A., Longe, O., Ambafi, J., Jack, K., Abd'Azeez, T., & Adeniyi, S. (2022). An overview of energy access solutions for rural healthcare facilities. *Energies*, 9554.
5. Amadi, H. N., Gobo, I. W., Uche-Ibe, U. B., & Ijeoma, R. C. (2025). Optimal designing of micro-grid systems with hybrid renewable energy technologies for sustainable environment. *International Journal of Scientific Research & Engineering Trends*, 11(5), 1–9.
6. Emenuvwe, O., Akporhonor, G., & Omokaro, H. (2022). Technical economic and environmental analysis on the potential of solar and wind micro-grid systems in Nigeria. *International Journal of Sustainable Energy Development (IJSED)*, 10(1), 470–481.
7. Sampson, I. (2023). Design of hybrid grid-tied solar power plant for constant energy supply in Nigeria. In *International Conference & Annual*

- General Meeting/Exhibition of the Nigerian Society of Chemical Engineers (NSChE).*
8. Ijeoma, R. C. (2025). Transformative energy practices and innovations: A path towards global energy equity. *SustainE*, 1(2), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.55366/suse.v1i2.14>.
 9. Rajanna, S., & Saini, R. P. (2016). Modelling of integrated renewable energy system for electrification of a remote area in India. *Renewable Energy*, 90, 175–187.
 10. Heyam, A. N., Hala, J., Christoph, E. K., Rafat, P., & Afif, A. L. (2022). Hybrid grid-tie electrification analysis of bio-shared renewable energy systems for domestic application. *Elsevier*, 103538.
 11. Ijeoma, R. C., & Briggs, I. (2018). Hydro power generation in Nigeria: Environmental ramifications. *IOSR Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineering (IOSR-JEEE)*, 13(5), 1–9.
 12. Khortsriwong, N., Boonraksa, P., Boonraksa, T., Fangsuwannarak, T., Boonsrirat, A., Pinthurat, W., & Marungsri, B. (2023). Performance of deep learning techniques for forecasting PV power generation: A case study on a 1.5 MW floating PV power plant. *Energies*, 16(5), 2119.
 13. Masoud, H., Brahman, F., & Shahram, J. (2020). Optimal electrical and thermal energy management of a residential energy hub, integrating demand response and energy storage system. *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, 78, 445–454.
 14. Hamid, K., Movahednia, M., & Shahram, J. (2022). A cooperative game approach for energy management of interconnected microgrids. *Electric Power Components and Systems*, 37(2), 127–145.